

The effect of perfluorosulfonic acid membrane molecular structure on excessive swelling in the context of PEM water electrolysis at elevated temperature and pressure

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ABSTRACT

Increasing the operating temperature and pressure of proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEM WE) enhances the process energy efficiency at high hydrogen production rates. However, it leads to membrane stability issues, such as excessive swelling. Despite its negative impact on membrane properties and system performance, this phenomenon is often overlooked in PEM WE field. In this study, excessive swelling of four commercial membranes exposed to 120 °C and 600 kPa for 800 h was investigated. All membranes showed increase in resistance. Degraded membranes were analysed using various techniques including SAXS, WAXS, DSC, and AFM. It was shown that the degree of excessive swelling depends mainly on membrane hydrophilicity and occurs even below the α -transition temperature. Longer side chains limit resistivity growth, likely due to larger structural domains and low tortuosity of the ion-conducting pathways. The study highlights the importance of membrane's internal nanomorphology on its performance and stability.

1. Introduction

To address climate change, the European Union has set an ambitious target to achieve greenhouse gas neutrality by 2050 [1]. Hydrogen is anticipated to play a pivotal role in the transformation of the energy system due to its wide range of applications. It can serve as a feedstock chemical in industrial production, be utilised for industrial heating, iron production, as a fuel in the transport sector, or it can act as an energy carrier in renewable power generation [2]. In this context, proton exchange membrane water electrolysis (PEM WE) represents one of the key electrochemical technologies for hydrogen production.

PEM WE offers several advantages. Compared to other technologies available for water splitting, it allows flexible changes in hydrogen production rate from nearly shutdown to high current density (around 2 A cm⁻² in commercial electrolyzers [3]). The relative compactness of the PEM electrolyzers allows for a small site footprint, and when operated at optimum conditions, PEM electrolyzers produce hydrogen of high purity with high energy efficiency. However, the need for corrosion-resistant titanium components and precious group metal (PGM) catalysts and

coatings drives up the investment costs of electrolyzers. Therefore, to improve the economic viability of the PEM WE technology, it is essential to further intensify hydrogen production in PEM water electrolyzers while ensuring their long-term stability. One potential approach of PEM water electrolysis intensification is increasing the operating temperature and pressure. This would improve energy efficiency by lowering the equilibrium voltage and, more importantly, by enhancing reaction kinetics, and proton conductivity of the membrane electrolyte. Increased pressure also improves mass transfer on the anode, enabling reaching higher current densities without reaching performance limitations.

PEM water electrolyzers typically operate at temperatures around 60–90 °C. Raising the operational temperature can introduce material stability challenges. Particularly, at temperatures above the boiling point of water (steam electrolysis), membrane drying becomes a significant issue [4]. In this regard, researchers have explored solutions such as use of composite membrane electrolytes with hydrophilic fillers, alternative membrane chemistries like doped polybenzimidazole, or phosphoric acid doping of conventional membranes based on perfluorinated sulfonic acid (PFSA) [5–8]. However, these approaches

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failed to provide competitive performance and stability.

Another approach to prevent membrane drying is to pressurise the electrolyser, maintaining water in its liquid state. However, experimental reports on the operation of PEM WE at elevated temperatures and pressures remain limited, and long-term performance and stability data are lacking. Existing studies have primarily used Nafion membranes as the electrolyte, exploring operational temperatures between 60 °C and 120 °C under pressures of 3 to 5 bar [9–12]. While operation at elevated temperature and pressure overall improves the energy efficiency, it also leads to an increase in hydrogen crossover [9,10]. Moreover, higher temperatures place additional stress on PFSA membranes, leading to accelerated membrane thinning and higher fluoride release rates [10,13]. Studies at elevated temperatures and pressures have also been conducted using composite membranes. In these studies, hydrophilic fillers such as TiO₂ or SiO₂ in Nafion matrix have been shown to be beneficial for the electrolyser performance at temperatures of up to 120 °C and pressure of 3 bar [14–16]. Similarly, composites of polysulfone nanofibers and Aquivion have been demonstrated to improve performance and to reduce gas crossover between electrode compartments [17].

Membrane degradation mechanisms such as mechanical stress, foreign ion contamination or membrane thinning due to chemical degradation are frequently considered in PEM WE studies [18–20]. However, the phenomenon of excessive swelling during prolonged operation (especially at elevated temperature and pressure) remains relatively underexplored, despite its significant impact on membrane performance. Moreover, PFSA membrane research is still predominantly focused on their application in PEM fuel cells, most of the available data on water sorption in membranes is focused on absorption of water vapour. Yet, it is the understanding of the long-term behaviour of PFSA membranes in liquid water, which is crucial for improving the durability and reliability of PEM water electrolysers.

The water sorption behaviour of PFSA membranes plays a fundamental role in defining their morphological, mechanical, and transport properties. Upon hydration, PFSA membranes exhibit phase separation due to their amphiphilic nature: the hydrophobic polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE) backbone forms a mechanically robust matrix, while the side chains with sulfonic acid (-SO₃H) groups interact with water molecules to form hydrophilic domains/channels through solvation [18]. The mechanical stability of the hydrated PFSA membranes is given by the balance between the internal pressure exerted by absorbed water and the resistance of the polymer matrix to deformation [18]. The hydrated domains, once sufficiently connected, create percolating networks that enable proton conduction. The mesoscale arrangement of these hydrophilic domains (including their size, connectivity, and spatial distribution) is a key factor in the ion transport and overall membrane performance [18]. This morphology arises from the interplay of polymer solvation, nanophase separation, and the molecular structure of the PFSA polymer. Moreover, the degree of crystallinity in the hydrophobic matrix, governed by the length of the polymer backbone between side chains, enhances mechanical stability by forming crystalline regions that resist swelling-induced deformation [18]. However, increasing backbone length and crystallinity often comes at the cost of reducing the density of sulfonic acid groups, thereby lowering ionic conductivity [18]. Thus, a trade-off exists between optimising mechanical integrity and ensuring sufficient charge carrier density. While presence of certain amount of water in the PFSA membrane is necessary in order to establish the ion-conducting two-phase structure, extensive amount of water leads to deterioration of its physico-chemical and mechanical properties [21–23].

The water absorption is temperature dependent. When immersed in liquid water (or exposed to water vapour of high enough activity), increasing temperature leads to an increase of water absorption by the polymer [18,24]. A crucial point on the temperature scale regarding PFSA membrane excessive swelling has been identified by Mališ et al. [21,22]. In these studies, it was shown that (protonated) Nafion 117

membrane immersed in liquid water at temperatures above approx. 110 °C and at increased pressure (500 and 700 kPa) rapidly loses its ionic conductivity and mechanical stability. No chemical changes (IR, NMR) were identified, and this degradation was ascribed to excessive swelling accompanied with changes of the membrane internal structure and crystallinity decrease. The temperature of 110 °C roughly coincides with the α -transition of Nafion (corresponding to a destabilisation of the electrostatic network that facilitates long-range polymer mobility [25, 26]) and the observed behaviour was therefore linked to this transition.

Most insights into the α -transition of PFSA membranes come from dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) of dry samples, where Nafion shows a sharp drop in elastic modulus near its α -transition temperature [26,27]. However, even moderate humidity (RH > 15%) suppresses this mechanical signature, highlighting that hydration significantly alters membrane behaviour [24,28,29]. Although hydrated PFSA membranes show no clear mechanical response at the α -transition temperature, dielectric spectroscopy (DS) reveals that α -relaxation still occurs and is linked to longitudinal polarisation of rod-like polymer aggregates [30–32]. DS studies on humidified Nafion (RH > 60%) identified a transition near 120 °C (or ~80 °C for membranes with lower equivalent weight), marked by a frequency shift of both α and β relaxations which was attributed to a conformational change driven by electrostatic repulsion between dissociated -SO₃ groups. The increased molecular rigidity associated with this conformation, together with strong hydrogen bonding in protonated Nafion, likely accounts for the suppressed viscoelastic response observed in DMA under humid conditions. In hydrated membranes at temperatures above the α -transition temperature, this conformational change likely enhances water absorption, as observed by Mališ et al. [21,22] and other authors [24,33].

In comparison to Nafion, Aquivion membranes feature shorter side chains. This design of chemical structure allows for higher crystallinity, improved mechanical properties and a higher α -transition temperature [34,35]. Therefore, Aquivion membranes may represent a more suitable option for application in PEM WE at elevated temperature and pressure compared to long-side-chained Nafions. In their comprehensive study, Moukheiber et al. [34] reported that the α -transition temperature of Aquivions (E79, E83, E87, E91, E110) reach values between 120 and 140 °C (based on their equivalent weight), while in case of Nafion (211, 111), it is around 100 °C. However, it is important to mention, that the values of α -transition temperature found for Nafion across different studies are not very consistent. In particular, the values available in the literature for Nafion 111, 117, 1035, 1110 vary between 60 °C and 115 °C (in all cases, the polymers have equivalent weight of 1100 g mol⁻¹ [18,29,34,36–39]).

The main aim of this study is to get closer insight on the relation between molecular structure of commercial PFSA membranes and their sensitivity to excessive swelling. This understanding will support the selection of materials best suited for the intended application. In order to achieve this target, the excessive swelling of PFSA membranes in liquid water at 120 °C and 600 kPa was followed with respect to their side-chain structure and equivalent weight. In particular, four different PFSA membranes were enclosed in a pressurised and heated conductivity cell with circulating water. Here, their ionic conductivity was monitored in the course of 800-h-long experiment. The membranes were then thoroughly characterised with various techniques to determine their morphology and physico-chemical changes induced by this hydrothermal treatment.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Deionised water used in the experiments was produced using a DIWA 3rica (Watek) reverse osmosis module, with a conductivity of freshly deionised water of 0.5 μ S cm⁻¹. The following chemicals were used for the preparation of solutions described in the next section (all analytical

grade purity): H₂O₂ (30 wt%, Lachner), H₂SO₄ (96 wt%, Lachner), NaCl (analytical grade, Penta), HCl (standard solution, Normanal Lachema), and NaOH (50 wt% solution, Acros Organics).

2.2. Hydrothermal treatment with ionic conductivity measurement

Four different commercially available PFSA membranes subjected to an environment of elevated temperature and pressure are summarised in Table 1. This selection of membranes was intended to cover a range of molecular structure parameters that influence membrane properties. The chosen membranes include those with long side chains (N117 and F940) and those with short side chains (AQE98 and AQE87). Side chain length is a critical factor, as it significantly impacts the α -transition temperature. The pairs of membranes with the same side chain length were selected to investigate the effect of equivalent weight, which influences both the α -transition temperature and polymer hydrophilicity. The effect of membrane reinforcement was also explored, using the F940 membrane as an example. F940 is solvent-cast, unlike the other membranes, which are produced by melt extrusion.

As the very first step, the membranes were activated and cleaned according to established procedure [21]. The as-received membranes were immersed in 80 °C deionised (DI) water for 60 min, then in 3 wt% H₂O₂ solution heated to 60 °C for 30 min and in 0.05 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ solution at 60 °C for 30 min. As the final step of the activation, the membranes were immersed in pure DI water at 60 °C for 120 min. During all steps, the solutions were gently stirred with a magnetic stirring bar.

For the ionic conductivity measurement, the activated membrane samples (1 cm × 6 cm) were enclosed in a conductivity cell and contacted with four Pt wires in a row (four-electrode arrangement) with distance between two (inner) sensing electrodes and (outer) feeding electrodes being 4 and 5.4 cm, respectively. Each half of the made-in-house cell featured a 1 cm × 6 cm × 1 mm groove to accommodate the membrane and allow the DI water to flow around the membrane. The cell was closed and tightened by eight M8 bolts using 5 N m torque. After assembly, the cell was placed inside an oven and connected to a hydraulic circuit with circulating DI water (0.5 cm³ min⁻¹), for schematic of the setup, see Fig. S1 in Supporting Information file. The cell inside the oven was heated to 120 °C and the circulating water was pressurised to 500 kPa of overpressure (to ensure the water stays liquid); the system remained at these conditions for 800 h. To minimise membrane contamination by metal ion traces the hydraulic circuit was equipped with an ion-exchange mixed bed resin column and all circuit components (except for metallic back-pressure regulators) were made of plastic. In particular, perfluoroalkoxy (Swagelok®) tubing, polyetheretherketone (PEEK) cell body and polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE) sealings were used. Throughout this hydrothermal treatment, the in-plane ohmic resistance (R_{Ω}) of the membrane was continuously monitored by means of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using an LCR bridge H8118 (Rohde & Schwarz). The impedance spectra were measured at an open circuit potential using 100 mV amplitude and 200 kHz to 20 Hz frequency range. From the obtained spectra (example spectra can be found in Fig. S2), ohmic resistance R_{Ω} was evaluated as the real part of impedance of the experimental point closest to the x axis

in the Nyquist diagram in the high frequency part of the spectrum using a Python-based algorithm.

2.3. Post mortem physico-chemical characterisation of membranes

Ion-exchange capacity (IEC) was evaluated by acid-base titration using an automatic potentiostatic titrator (HI 932, Hanna Instruments). All solutions were prepared from DI water. First, a small piece of the membrane (1.5 cm × 1 cm) was dropped inside 60 mL of N₂-purged 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaCl solution where H⁺ ions in the membrane were exchanged for Na⁺ ions. After stabilisation of pH (around 5 min), the solution with the membrane sample was titrated with approx. 0.01 mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution. The exact concentration of the NaOH solution was determined by titration using a standard 0.05 mol dm⁻³ solution of HCl. After the titration, the membrane samples (in Na⁺ form) were removed, rinsed in DI water, and converted back to the H⁺ form by 30 min immersion in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ HCl followed by careful rinsing in DI water (first under running water and then the samples were left over night in around 50 cm³ of DI water). These re-protonated (RP) membranes were again titrated with NaOH solution following the same procedure. After the second titration, the membranes were re-protonated again, tapped with a paper cloth to remove droplets on their surface and weighted (MS304TS, Mettler Toledo). Finally, the membranes were dried (10 min, 90 °C in air environment) and weighted again. Water content was determined from the mass of the samples before and after drying.

The internal structure of the membranes was investigated using Small and Wide-angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS and WAXS). The experiments were performed using a pinhole camera (modified molecular metrology system; Rigaku, Japan) attached to a microfocussed X-ray beam generator (Rigaku MicroMax 003) operated at 50 kV and 0.6 mA (30 W). The camera was equipped with a vacuum-compatible version of Pilatus3 R 300 K hybrid photon-counting detector. A setup upgrade made by SAXSLAB enabled the detector to stay aligned with the beam. Three different sample-to-detector distances – 50, 400, and 1400 mm were used to cover a wider q -range. The exposure time used was 4 h. The scattering vector, q , is defined by Eq. (1), where $\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$ is the radiation wavelength and 2θ is the scattering angle. Measured diffractograms were fitted according to a procedure described in detail in Section S2 of the SI file.

$$q = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta) \quad (1)$$

The WAXS peak deconvolution procedure was performed using Fityk software version 1.3.1 [40]. Crystalline reflections were modelled using Lorentzian functions and the amorphous halos using Gaussian functions. The degree of crystallinity is calculated as the ratio of the integrated area of all crystalline peaks to the total scattering intensity after background subtraction. A more detailed information on crystallinity determination procedure can be found in the SI in Section S2.

Scanning probe microscope Dimension ICON PT (Bruker) was used for observation of the samples in Peak Force Quantitative Mechanical Property Mapping (PF QNM) mode. The observation provides the topography of the surface depicted as a height image, local elastic properties of the sample as DMT modulus and local adhesivity of the sample. Bruker silicon nitride probes Scanasyt-air were utilised with tip

Table 1

Overview of studied membranes with their specifications; t_{AR} and t_A stand for thicknesses in the as-received and activated states, EW denotes equivalent weight (g / SO₃⁻), LSC and SSC denote long-side-chained and short-side-chained membranes, respectively. Listed abbreviations are used to refer to the specific membrane samples studied in this work.

Membrane	Abbreviation	Manufacturer	t_{AR} /μm	t_A /μm	EW	Features
Nafion N117	N117	Chemours	183	210	1100	LSC, extruded
Fumapem F-940-RF	F940	Fumatech	40	70	870	LSC, reinforced, cast
Aquivion E87-05S	AQE87	Solvay	50	76	870	SSC, extruded
Aquivion E98-05S	AQE98	Solvay	50	66	980	SSC, extruded

apex diameter of 2 to 3 nm and the spring constant $k = 0.4 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ during measurement of as-received samples. Bruker silicon nitride probes Scanasyt-fluid+ with tip apex diameter of 2 to 4 nm and the spring constant $k = 0.7 \text{ N m}^{-1}$ were utilised for measurement of wet samples (activated and treated membranes). No damage of samples caused by the scanning probe was observed for the as-received and activated membranes. Each sample was examined on both sides. Each side was examined at two or three spots. Range of scan sizes: 10 μm , 3 μm , 1 μm , 350 nm. The resulting images were evaluated by NanoScope Analysis 1.50 software. Selected topographical images were processed with a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis with stopband filter 55 nm to increase their clarity.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to investigate the states of water in the samples. Prior to insertion of the samples inside the calorimeter, the wet membrane samples were placed in an open aluminium pan and were put in a concealed containers containing solutions of NaCl (10 mg cm^{-3}) for a duration of one week in order to equilibrate the samples with water vapour at room temperature. After that, the aluminium pans were hermetically sealed. For the measurement, Q2000 differential scanning calorimeter was used. The procedure was performed in an inert atmosphere of N_2 with a gas flow rate of 50 $\text{cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The measurements were carried out in cooling-heating regime, i.e. from +20 to $-70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and back to +20 $^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature change rate was 10 $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$. Data were evaluated from cooling and heating curves using TA Instruments Trios software. The samples were then dried at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 h. Water content for DSC-measured samples was established from their weights before and after drying.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hydrothermal treatment and conductivity monitoring

Activated membranes were exposed to 800-h hydrothermal treatment in liquid water at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 600 kPa, during which the conductivity cell with the membrane sample was continuously monitored by EIS, allowing to evaluate the time evolution of the cell ohmic resistance, R_Ω . As shown in Fig. 1, starting from about 1 k Ω , R_Ω gradually increased for all tested membranes. The most significant increase occurred in the cell containing the reinforced membrane (F940), where R_Ω rapidly reached several hundreds of k Ω . This suggests practically complete loss of ionic conductivity of the membrane. In contrast, the remaining membranes showed more stable performance. In particular, the least pronounced change in R_Ω was observed for the cell with AQE98, which exhibited a 13% increase in R_Ω , followed by N117 with a 19% increase and AQE87 with an increase of 58%. Notably, the rate of R_Ω increase varies over time and differs between membranes. For N117 and both Aquivion membranes (AQE87 and AQE98), the most pronounced rise in R_Ω is observed during the first 200 h of the hydrothermal treatment and then slows down. After the initial 200 h period, the AQE87 membrane shows a steady R_Ω increase with a slope $dR_\Omega/dt \approx 0.4 \text{ } \Omega \text{ h}^{-1}$. On the other hand, N117 demonstrated the slowest R_Ω increase with $dR_\Omega/dt \approx 0.03 \text{ } \Omega \text{ h}^{-1}$. Therefore, from a long-term perspective, N117 seems to be the most stable among the studied membranes under the conditions of the experiment.

After cooling and removal from the conductivity cell, the membranes were further analysed. It is clear that the state of the membrane at

Fig. 1. Time evolution of R_Ω of the conductivity cell with the membrane samples enclosed in it at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 600 kPa. Each line represents a separate measurement. ΔR_Ω denotes the ohmic resistance change over 800 h while the time derivative dR_Ω/dt corresponds to the average slope of linear regressions fitted to the curves for times above 200 h.

ambient temperature and pressure differs from that during hydrothermal treatment. However, at least part of the structural changes is clearly preserved. The first inspection after the hydrothermal treatment revealed a complete collapse (loss of mechanical integrity and volume) of the F940 membrane. A significant portion of the ionomer from the F940 membrane appeared to delaminate from the reinforcing mesh, and it was flushed out of the cell by the circulating water, which explains the dramatic increase in R_{Ω} . The extruded membranes (N117, AQE87, AQE98) became wrinkled (illustrative photos in Fig. S3) and fragile. The prominent wrinkling of the extruded membranes was very probably caused by membrane swelling while being constricted inside the conductivity cell.

The complete mechanical failure of the F940 membrane is likely related to its low EW (high hydrophilicity) in combination to its fabrication process and/or the presence of the reinforcing mesh. Although literature sources do not suggest that solvent casting inherently produces unstable membranes [18,41,42], the resulting quality strongly depends on fabrication parameters such as the choice of solvent, casting temperature, and post-treatment conditions [43,44]. Since the exact manufacturing procedure of the commercial membranes is confidential, the impact of manufacturing conditions on the observed failure can only be speculated. The membrane was selected for this study due to the presence of the reinforcing mesh intended to suppress dimensional changes associated with swelling. However, under the extreme experimental conditions applied here, the ionomer undergoes extreme swelling, while the reinforcing mesh remains dimensionally stable. This pronounced mismatch in volumetric expansion likely generates substantial internal stresses at the ionomer-mesh interface, ultimately leading to mechanical failure manifested as delamination of the ionomer phase from the non-swelling reinforcing structure. It should be noted that the F940 membrane was primarily developed for PEM fuel cell applications, where it would not be exposed to such extreme conditions.

After dismantling from the conductivity cell, dimensional and volumetric changes of each membrane were evaluated and are presented in Table 2. However, due to their increased fragility and irregular shape, precise measurement of their dimensions was difficult and quantitative value on these numbers is limited. Estimated error in length determination is about 10–20% (depending on the membrane) and thickness and width about 10%. This can result in up to 30–40% error in determination of the volume and resistivity ρ (shown later) after the hydrothermal treatment. While the estimated errors imply that the presented values of volume and resistivity are rather unreliable, they show meaningful correlation with other quantities shown in the manuscript (such as Fig. 5, 9 and S47).

It can be noticed that all membranes swell anisotropically – both Aquivions showed the most pronounced change in their thickness, whereas N117 exhibited the most noticeable change in length. Anisotropic swelling of extruded membranes is a well-documented phenomenon, with reduced swelling typically observed along the extrusion direction [45–47]. A similar behaviour has been reported for pre-stretched membranes [48]. In both cases, the processing-induced preferential orientation of the membrane's internal nanostructure governs the anisotropy in swelling as well as anisotropy in transport properties. In our experiments, the lowest swelling observed in the width (w) direction identifies it as the extrusion direction. Thus, the dimensional change data indicate that charge transport was probed along an axis

perpendicular to the membrane extrusion direction for all extruded membranes. Overall, AQE98 proved to be the most dimensionally stable of investigated membranes under the experimental conditions, which can be advantageous for practical applications such as fabrication of membrane-electrode assemblies.

Using Eq. (2), membrane resistivity ρ was calculated from the measured dimensions at both the beginning and the end of the experiment. The symbols t , w and L in Eq. (2) correspond to membrane thickness, width and length, respectively. While absolute values of R_{Ω} include minor contributions from the wires and contacts in the whole experimental setup, the majority of changes in R_{Ω} can be attributed to the resistance within the membrane (and its contact to the sensing electrodes). As shown in Table 3, AQE87 exhibited significant changes in material properties, resulting in a 247%-increase in resistivity. Interestingly, resistivity of N117 increased by only 7%.

$$\rho = \frac{R_{\Omega} \cdot t \cdot w}{L} \quad (2)$$

There is a fundamental difference in the information conveyed by changes in R_{Ω} and ρ . The parameter R_{Ω} is more application-relevant, as its variation directly corresponds to changes in membrane resistance in an operating electrolyser and thus to associated voltage losses. The changes in R_{Ω} reflect both the dimensional changes of the membrane and the changes in the ion transport in the material. In contrast, changes in ρ provide deeper insight into how structural changes affect ion transport within the membrane since it describes only the effects related to the actual material properties.

Based on the data in Table 3, ion transport in short-side-chained Aquivion membranes appears to be significantly disrupted by the changes induced by the hydrothermal treatment. Conversely, despite its relatively large volume increase, the ion conducting network within N117 appears to be more resistant to degradation of its ion-transport properties. We can speculate that this pronounced difference is related to the different side chain lengths of the ionomers.

3.2. Ion-exchange capacity and water content determination

To provide a basic understanding of the observed phenomena and to elucidate the origin of the observed changes of the charge transport in the hydrothermally treated membranes, an ion-exchange capacity (IEC) of the membranes before and after the treatment was determined based on acid-base titration (with NaOH). After the titration, the membrane samples were re-protonated (RP), i.e. converted back to the H^+ -form, in HCl to remove any metal ions from their structure. Subsequently, the IEC of RP membranes was determined again. The results are summarised in Fig. 2a. The difference in IEC between 'activated' (samples before the hydrothermal treatment) and 'treated' membranes, observed in all four samples, may suggest a loss of $-SO_3H$ groups available for ion exchange. However, for the extruded membranes (N117, AQE87 and AQE98), this diminished IEC was fully recovered through re-protonation. This reversible loss of IEC suggests potential foreign ion contamination of membranes during the hydrothermal treatment, likely due to residual ions from the circulating DI water or metallic back-pressure regulators. Most importantly, these results indicate that any possible changes to the internal membrane morphology (induced by the hydrothermal

Table 2

Changes in dimensions of membrane samples after the hydrothermal treatment at 120 °C and 600 kPa for duration of 800 h. The abbreviations denote following parameters: t = thickness, w = width, L = length, V = volume.

Membrane	$\Delta t / \%$	$\Delta w / \%$	$\Delta L / \%$	$\Delta V / \%$
N117	+47	+19	+100	+250
AQE87	+133	+26	+33	+292
AQE98	+68	+12	+26	+137

Table 3

Resistivity values of the membranes at the start and at the end of the experiment at 120 °C and 600 kPa (the value of resistance used for the calculation includes contribution from the conductivity cell).

Membrane	ρ at $t = 0$ h at 120 °C /mΩ m	ρ at $t = 800$ h at 120 °C /mΩ m	$\Delta \rho / \%$
N117	23 ± 1	24 ± 1	+7
F940	33 ± 2	-	-
AQE87	19 ± 1	66 ± 4	+247
AQE98	15 ± 1	25 ± 2	+68

Fig. 2. Values of a) ion-exchange capacity of activated membranes, hydrothermally treated membranes and their re-protonated versions; b) water content in activated and treated membranes (drying at 90 °C for 10 min). Values represent the arithmetic mean obtained from analyses of two membrane samples. RP denotes “re-protonated”.

treatment) did not influence the amount of accessible $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups as suggested previously [21,22]. That is, there is no alteration in membrane morphology that would result in change of the surface-to-volume ratio leading to an increase or decrease in the IEC. In the case of the hydrothermally treated F940 membrane, the pronounced decrease of IEC values clearly corresponds to the significant loss of ionomer during the experiment.

The IEC results suggested that during the hydrothermal treatment the membranes become partially contaminated by foreign cations, which could be a reason for the observed increase in membrane resistivity ρ (and resistance R_Ω). To confirm or exclude this hypothesis, another sample of AQE87 membrane (exhibiting the most pronounced IEC drop after the treatment, i.e. potentially highest level of contamination by foreign ions during the experiment) was exposed to hydrothermal treatment for 800 h. Then, the R_Ω of this membrane in the conductivity cell was measured by EIS at room temperature. After that, the sample was removed from the cell, re-protonated, inserted back in the cell and its R_Ω at room temperature was measured again. Since the re-protonation did not lead to a measurable decrease in R_Ω , it was concluded that foreign ion contamination was not the cause of the R_Ω changes observed during the hydrothermal treatment (results presented in Fig. S4).

Important insights were gained by assessing the water content in the membranes. It was determined by comparing mass of the membrane samples measured before (m_{wet}) and after drying at 90 °C for 10 min (m_{dry}) using Eq. (3).

$$\text{wt. \% H}_2\text{O} = \frac{m_{\text{wet}} - m_{\text{dry}}}{m_{\text{wet}}} \quad (3)$$

As shown in Fig. 2b, the hydrothermal treatment significantly increased the water content in all samples. AQE98 (EW = 980 g mol⁻¹) showed lower affinity towards water than AQE87 (EW = 870 g mol⁻¹), which is in agreement with expectation based on EW value. On the other hand, N117 displayed relatively high water uptake despite its higher equivalent weight (EW = 1100 g mol⁻¹). Due to differences in side chain length, direct comparison between N117 and the Aquivion membranes based solely on EW is not straightforward. A much more suitable approach for comparison in this context is to subtract the molecular mass of the side chain from that of the monomer unit and calculate a new “equivalent weight” corresponding to the molecular mass of the backbone per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. From this value, the most illustrative step is to determine the number of tetrafluoroethylene (TFE) units in the repeating unit – in other words, the length of the backbone between the side chains. The polymer hydrophilicity then decreases with increasing length of the PTFE backbone between side chains (more TFE units). The number of TFE units per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group is 7.0 for AQE98, 6.7 for N117

and 5.9 for AQE87, indicating that AQE98 should be the least hydrophilic, followed by N117, while AQE87 should be the most hydrophilic. The number of TFE units also reflects the membrane’s tendency to crystallise. More crystalline polymers typically absorb less water due to a stiffer matrix that restricts swelling. Based solely on the backbone structure, N117 would not be expected to absorb significantly more water than AQE98. However, a clear difference was observed: N117 absorbed about 63% water, compared to 48% for AQE98 and 80% for AQE87. The relatively high water uptake of N117 may be attributed to its longer side chains, lower crystallinity, or variations in microstructure and manufacturing history.

In any case, the increase in water content correlates positively with the rise in R_Ω observed during hydrothermal treatment. The relative change in R_Ω follows the sequence: AQE87 > N117 > AQE98, which mirrors the trends in water uptake and relative volume change (Table 2, Fig. S5). This indicates that the change in R_Ω is largely driven by water absorption and associated volume changes.

Increase in R_Ω (and ρ) after swelling of PFSA membranes with excessive amounts of water can be expected. According to Gebel [23], upon water uptake, two primary effects influence proton transport: dilution of the charge-transport groups and morphological reorganisation (i.e., domain development). At low to moderate hydration levels, increased water content enhances ionic conductivity (decreases ρ) by promoting a favourable morphology for proton conduction (decrease of tortuosity). However, beyond a certain hydration threshold, further water uptake leads to conductivity loss due to charge dilution (the curve of dependence of conductivity on water content exhibits a maximum). At excessively high water contents, the membrane’s behaviour resembles that of a colloidal dispersion.

Our results showed relatively small ρ increase (7%) in case of N117 (Table 3). This clearly documents that the amount of water introduced inside N117 during the hydrothermal treatment was not high enough to significantly disrupt its ionic conductivity. In contrast, for both AQE98 and AQE87 the ρ increase was more pronounced with 68% and 247%-change, respectively. This indicates that the longer side chains in N117 offer greater stability against conductivity loss during excessive swelling probably due to the character of the morphology that they create. The intuition that the observed differences in charge transport are primarily governed by internal morphology changes is supported by the literature, which indicates that side-chain chemistry has little to no influence on proton and water transport, with overall transport properties mainly determined by water content and internal morphology [49–51].

3.3. Internal structure analysis by SAXS and WAXS

SAXS analysis was employed to investigate the changes in the

internal morphology of the membranes occurring during the experiment. The samples were measured in the as-received state, after the activation and after undergoing the hydrothermal treatment. For illustration, the resulting 1D scattering curves of N117 are shown in Fig. 3, curves of other membranes are depicted in Fig. S6. The SAXS profiles of all samples possess two distinct correlation peaks. The origins of these two peaks are still debated. At higher values of q , there is the “ionomer peak” which comes from either scattering on the hydrophilic domains [18] or on the hydrophobic polymer aggregates [52,53]. At lower values, there is the “matrix knee” connected to crystallinity of the polymer [18,54]. As can be seen from Fig. 3, the positions of both peaks shift towards lower q values with hydration which reflects the expansion of the internal structure.

The scattering vector values (q -vectors) and corresponding evaluated d -spacings ($d = 2\pi q^{-1}$) are summarised in Table S1. The d -spacing for the ionomer peak and the matrix knee can be interpreted as the distances between the hydrophobic polymer aggregates (or hydrophilic domains) and crystallites, respectively. The data from Table S1 are visualised in Fig. 4. In the as-received state, the membranes exhibit a compact internal structure, with no remarkable differences observed even between the individual membrane types. Upon activation, the internal structure expands, as indicated by increased d -spacing of both the matrix knee and the ionomer peak. Again, differences between individual membrane types with exception of F940 are negligible. In contrast, the structure expansion following the hydrothermal treatment is dramatically more pronounced.

The correlation distances between the scattering entities show linear dependence on water content in the membranes (Fig. 4c and d) demonstrating that this expansion is driven/accompanied by water uptake. The linear relationship between water content and domain spacing in Nafion membranes was well documented before [55–57]. Interestingly, our data show that this applies regardless of the PFSA membrane type and state which suggests similarity of the structural features and types of interactions between all investigated membranes and water. Hydrothermally treated F940 seems to be the exception from this trend. In this case, the ionomer peak d -spacing does not fall into the established linear relationship, while the matrix knee d -spacing follows the expected behaviour reasonably well.

Another noteworthy feature in the data presented in Fig. 4c and d is the difference in the slopes of the two d -spacing dependencies on water content. The matrix knee d -spacing increases nearly five times more steeply with rising water content compared to the ionomer peak d -spacing. This discrepancy in slope may reflect reduction in crystallinity

Fig. 3. 1D SAXS curves in the log-log scale for series of N117 membrane samples.

during the hydrothermal treatment, as discussed later.

A closer examination of the ionomer peak d -spacing for membranes in the activated and hydrothermally treated states reveals a mismatch between macroscopic and nano-scale structural expansion. Upon hydrothermal treatment, the membrane volume increased by factors of 3.5, 3.9 and 2.4 in case of N117, AQE87 and AQE98, respectively. In contrast, the corresponding nanoscale changes were substantially larger: the third power of d -spacing (d^3) increased by factors of 10.5, 23.5 and 6 for N117, AQE87 and AQE98, respectively. Consequently, the apparent nanostructure expansion is approximately 3–6 times larger than in the case of the macroscopic membrane dimensions. This behaviour is characteristic of non-affine swelling and is commonly attributed to coalescence or aggregation of the scattering entities within the membrane [18,58].

As was explored above, the membranes exhibit significant differences in their affinity towards water. Among the extruded membranes, AQE87 shows the highest, N117 medium and AQE98 lowest degree of water swelling after the hydrothermal treatment. This trend is also reflected in the expansion of their internal structure. As already mentioned, crystallinity of the membranes is expected to play an important role in the absorption of water. Therefore, to investigate the role of the crystalline structure, wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) was used to characterise the membranes, in their as-received and activated states, and after the hydrothermal treatment. Fig. S8 shows the WAXS diffractograms and their fits used to determine crystallinity with respect to the dry portion of the samples (excluding the contribution of water). As depicted in Fig. 5a, in the as-received state, N117 exhibits the highest degree of crystallinity, while AQE87 is the least crystalline. This is somewhat surprising as based on the molecular structure, AQE98 should be the most crystalline as it has the most TFE units per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. Moreover, this effect should be amplified by the short side chains that allow for more efficient packing of the backbone (in comparison with the long side chains in N117) [18]. However, same as many other properties of the PFSA membranes, the crystallinity is highly dependent on the history of the samples, including the manufacturing process, which can explain this discrepancy. Also, there is generally a wide spread of crystallinity values reported in the literature for PFSA membranes (5–30%) [18,34,59,60]. This can be explained by differences in manufacturing, as well as experimental conditions and methodology of crystallinity determination.

Upon activation, all membranes showed a reduction in crystallinity. The hydrothermal treatment led to a further decrease in crystallinity in N117, F940 and AQE87. As shown in Fig. 5b, F940 exhibits the most pronounced decrease in crystallinity between the activated and treated states. Interestingly, despite the severe degradation observed in the treated F940, the material still displays a semicrystalline character – likely originating from the PTFE reinforcing mesh. The curious behaviour of AQE98, which exhibits an increase in crystallinity after the hydrothermal treatment, may stem from sample heterogeneity or, potentially, from a measurement error, as the WAXS profiles are largely dominated by water signal (as shortly discussed below).

The crystallinity reduction following significant water uptake agrees with observations reported in literature [22,55]. It is likely that the high degree of water absorption during hydrothermal treatment was facilitated by disruption of crystalline domains (and/or vice versa). This is supported by the inverse correlation between crystallinity and water uptake: after the treatment, crystallinity of the hydrothermally treated samples decreases in the order AQE98 > N117 > AQE87, while the extent of water absorption follows exactly opposite trend.

It needs to be noted, that the WAXS results were impacted by the significant water content in all activated and treated samples, which introduced errors in the crystallinity evaluation precision. The percentages at the foot of the columns in Fig. 5a indicate the portion of WAXS diffractogram's area belonging to the polymer matrix – the lower the percentage, the lower the reliability of the crystallinity value. However, while the absolute crystallinity values in the samples

Fig. 4. Quantitative parameters of the internal structure of tested samples evaluated from SAXS experiments in terms of distances between a) ionomer domains/aggregates, b) crystallites and c), d) correlation of these distances with water content.

Fig. 5. Values of a) crystallinity of membrane samples in as-received, activated and hydrothermally treated states, b) the relative change of crystallinity with respect to the as-received state. The percentages at the foot of the columns in a) indicate the portion of the WAXS diffractogram area belonging to the polymer matrix (remainder is water).

(especially those with high contents of water) should be interpreted with caution, the results are still qualitatively meaningful and clearly demonstrate that water absorption decreases crystallinity of membranes (and decreased crystallinity promotes further water absorption).

3.4. Surface morphology probing by AFM

Surface morphology of the membrane samples was examined using AFM. Selected images are provided in Section S3 of the Supporting

Information. The samples were probed in their as-received, activated, and hydrothermally treated states. The presence of water in the activated and treated membranes reduced the resolution of the adhesivity mapping. Moreover, analysis of the hydrothermally treated samples was challenging due to their uneven surfaces and mechanical softness, which frequently led to probe-induced damage.

Both sides of the membranes were investigated at different resolutions. Overview scans (10 and 3 μm scan sizes) revealed distinct morphological differences between the two sides of each membrane,

likely originating from the fabrication process. Images with a 1 μm scan size were used to identify suitable regions free of surface defects or contamination for detailed imaging. High-resolution scans (350 nm scan size) revealed a corrugated and inhomogeneous surface morphology. To emphasise fine structural details, selected topographical images were mathematically processed using an FFT analysis with stopband filter 55 nm.

AFM observations revealed two-phase structure on the surface of samples. An example shown in Fig. 6 for the as-received AQE98 membrane demonstrates strong correlation among the topography, adhesivity, and elastic modulus maps. A clear two-phase character is evident: areas with lower modulus (softer) also exhibit higher adhesivity (stickier). These softer features are more readily indented/pressed by the AFM probe and therefore appear as topographically depressed. Such regions are likely less reinforced by the polymer matrix and correspond to more swollen areas. This phenomenon can be observed on as-received samples N117 and AQE87 as well. Similarly, activated N117 and AQE98 samples show topography-modulus correlation.

As shown in Fig. 7 for the N117, the height difference between the depressed and elevated regions increases with the degree of swelling (from the as-received to the treated state).

The lateral sizes and distances of the soft, sunken features were visually quantified and subsequently statistically analysed, with results

presented in Fig. S9. No clear relationship between these parameters and the membrane type was observed. An increase of both parameters from the activated state to the treated state is observed for all membranes. However, expected minimum for the as-received state was not confirmed. It must be recognised that the changes to the membrane surface caused by water exposure are complex and significant.

The AFM-derived dimensions were also compared with SAXS data in Fig. S10. The sizes obtained from AFM show partial agreement with the matrix knee d -spacing, particularly in the as-received and activated states, whereas this correlation diminishes after hydrothermal treatment. No such agreement was found between the AFM sizes and the ionomer peak d -spacing.

These results indicate that the AFM-observed surface features differ from the morphology of the bulk, which is an often-observed phenomenon in complex polymer systems.

3.5. Water states investigation by DSC

As shown above, the increasing water content in PFSA membranes seems to be the main cause of the changes in their behaviour. Therefore, to obtain more insight into the properties of the water embedded in the membrane structure, the samples were analysed by DSC. Sample F940 was not further studied due to its significant deterioration during the

Fig. 6. Example AFM scans of as-received AQE98 showing the two-phased morphology of the surface; a) measured topography, b) FFT-filtered topography, c) adhesion, d) modulus.

Fig. 7. FFT-filtered topography AFM scans (350 nm scale) of N117 in different states; a) as-received – vertical scale 2.6 nm, b) activated – vertical scale 8.7 nm, c) treated – vertical scale 15.9 nm.

hydrothermal treatment.

An example of DSC thermogram is depicted in Fig. S44. It is a well-known fact that a certain part of the water molecules in PFSA membranes does not freeze due to strong interactions with the $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups (forming its solvation shell) and/or confinement in nano-sized hydrophilic channels [18,61–63]. Thus, the values of enthalpy associated with water freezing (and melting) obtained from the DSC experiments were used to calculate the amount of (non-)freezing water in the membrane samples. The calculations (Eq. S1, S2) were done assuming that freezing water behaves like bulk water (i.e. the specific fusion and melting enthalpies of freezing water in the membrane are equal to values for bulk water). Finally, by subtracting the amount of freezing water from the total water content in the samples, it is possible to obtain the amount of water that does not freeze during the DSC scan (non-freezing water; Eq. S(3)).

Fig. 8 combines information about ratio of mass of water to mass of dry membrane together with the numbers of freezing ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}}$) and non-freezing ($\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}}$) water molecules per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. It reveals a clear distinction between the behaviour of Aquivion membranes and the N117 membrane. In the case of Aquivions, most of the water introduced during the hydrothermal treatment is non-freezing, i.e., in close contact with the $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups, whereas in N117, the majority of the newly introduced water freezes.

The $\lambda_{\text{freezing}}$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}}$ values in activated N117 reached 5 and 21, respectively. In hydrothermally treated N117, $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 33$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 44$ were found. These values are in a reasonable agreement with data from literature. For example, in a “pre-boiled” N117, values of $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 8.3$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 12.4$ were found by Kalapos et al. [64], while $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 5.6$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 9.1$ were reported by Lue et al. [62]. Finally, Alberti et al. [24] immersed “pre-boiled pre-dried” N117 membranes in liquid water contained in a small Teflon vessels; the vessels were then enclosed and heated to various temperatures. After 220 h of equilibration at 120 °C, they received total λ (i.e. $\lambda_{\text{freezing}} + \lambda_{\text{non-freezing}}$) ≈ 36 , while total $\lambda \approx 71$, i.e. value closer to the hydrothermally treated samples obtained in our experiments, was reached after 200 h at 140 °C.

In contrast to the extensively studied Nafion, reports on water state distributions in Aquivion membranes remain scarce. An exception is a thorough study by Guan et al. [65] that investigated differences in dispersion cast LSC and SSC membranes. In agreement with our results, they found that LSC membrane hydrated at 30 °C exhibited higher proportion of freezing water ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 8.2$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 1.2$; 87% freezing) than SSC membrane ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 11.0$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 2.4$; 82% freezing), but the difference was not as dramatic. A striking discrepancy with our results is the substantially higher fraction of freezing water reported for their SSC membranes. However, in their study, membranes were prepared by solution casting from an

Fig. 8. H_2O content in the membrane samples before and after the thermal treatment, different colours indicate proportions of freezing and non-freezing water calculated from DSC data together with corresponding λ values. A and T denote “activated” and hydrothermally “treated” membrane, respectively. “Minimum” freezing water corresponds to the amount of water that was measured in samples that were dried at 25 °C in air (RH \sim 38%) – such samples did not exhibit the freezing/melting peak in DSC. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

isopropanol/water/ethanol mixture at room temperature, followed by annealing. The observed differences in water accommodation can therefore be attributed to variations in internal membrane morphology, which are expected to arise from the polymer chain assembly driven by solvent–polymer interactions, in contrast to the melt-extruded membranes investigated in our work [43].

The morphological origin of the difference in (non-)freezing water content between Nafion and Aquivion membranes observed in this work is supported by the study of Álvarez-Gallego et al. [66]. They showed a difference in water state distributions between Nafion 117 ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 11.5$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 9.3$; 55% freezing) and Nafion 112 ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 0.8$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 9.7$; 8% freezing). Both these membranes are

Fig. 9. Illustration of how changes in water states $\lambda_{\text{treated}} - \lambda_{\text{activated}}$ relate to changes in observed quantities, $X_{\text{treated}} - X_{\text{activated}}$, where X is: a) crystalline domain d -spacing, b) ionomer domain/aggregate d -spacing and c) resistivity ρ . d) Relationship between changes in resistivity and changes in d -spacing.

fabricated by melt extrusion and their distinct behaviour was attributed to different pretreatment protocols: Nafion 117 was pre-boiled, whereas Nafion 112 was annealed. Nevertheless, an additional parameter that may have contributed to the observed differences (and which may also be relevant in our case) is the substantial difference in membrane thickness, namely ~ 180 and ~ 50 μm (both in dry state) for Nafion 117 and Nafion 112, respectively.

Interesting and relevant results were obtained also by Lin et al. [67], who reported that an increase in non-freezing water content correlates with a decrease in hydrophilic domain size in pre-stretched, dispersion-cast Nafion membranes. Prior to stretching, the membrane exhibited 59% of freezing water ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 11.0$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 7.5$), whereas after stretching the portion of freezing water reduced to 24% ($\lambda_{\text{freezing}} \approx 4$ and $\lambda_{\text{non-freezing}} \approx 13$). As discussed in the context of the dimensional changes presented in Table 2, melt extrusion induces internal structural effects in PFSA membranes that are analogous to those caused by uniaxial stretching. Consequently, the fabrication conditions during melt extrusion of AQE98 and AQE87 membranes may promote morphologies similar to those obtained at high draw ratios, plausibly leading to smaller hydrophilic domains. The absence of a comparably pronounced effect in N117 remains unclear; it may be related to its greater thickness, the differences in extrusion conditions during industrial fabrication, or it may be linked to the different side-chain chemistry.

The large portion of non-freezing water (lack of bulk-like water) in Aquivions points to small hydrophilic domains (large surface to volume ratio) due to which most of the water molecules are always in the vicinity of the $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups and thus cannot form the freezing bulk phase.

Based on existing literature, it can be assumed that up to three molecular layers of water adjacent to the walls of a porous material exhibit non-freezing behaviour [68]. Thus, in Aquivion membranes, the majority of water channels are expected to enclose roughly six water molecules between the channel walls, corresponding to an average channel thickness of 1.7 nm in both the activated and treated states (assuming an effective diameter of a water molecule to be 0.28 nm [69]).

The presented differences in water accommodation inside the nanoscale morphology of the membranes seem to be linked to the extent of changes in resistivity ρ discussed above (Fig. 1 and Table 3). This is illustrated in Fig. 9. By plotting change in λ ($\Delta\lambda = \lambda_{\text{treated}} - \lambda_{\text{activated}}$) against change in d -spacing and ρ , Fig. 9a and b show that the microstructural expansion probed by SAXS (Fig. 4) correlates with the change in total water content. In contrast, the change in ρ correlates more strongly with the change in amount of only non-freezing water – lower levels of non-freezing water in the Aquivion membranes correspond to increased ρ (Fig. 9c). Furthermore, the lack of correlation between changes in d -spacing and ρ (Fig. 9d) suggests that charge transport decline is more influenced by how water is accommodated within the membrane than by structural expansion alone.

Nonetheless, it is important to note that the structural changes induced in N117 (although they do not seem to impair intrinsic proton transport) still have negative consequences, such as reduced mechanical strength. In addition, the pronounced volume expansion may be problematic in practical applications.

3.6. Geometric conception of the membrane nanostructure

The present results raise three unresolved questions.

1. How can **AQE87** exhibit the most pronounced microstructural expansion after the hydrothermal treatment while simultaneously showing the highest water uptake, yet with nearly all incorporated water remaining in the non-freezing state?
2. Why do Aquivion membranes display a more pronounced degradation of ion transport properties compared to **N117**?
3. What is the role of non-freezing water in the resistivity increase?

In this section, these observations are discussed using a deliberately simplified geometric model of the membrane nanostructure. The model is not intended to provide a quantitative description of membrane morphology, but rather to serve as a conceptual framework for addressing the questions raised above.

In the first approximation, the membrane structure can be viewed as a series of parallel identical cylinders. Each cylinder with volume (V_{cylinder}) represents one aggregate of polymer chains surrounded by a tubular shell of corresponding amount of water ($V_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$). This simple model is based on studies of PFSA dispersions and membranes, which have concluded that the fundamental morphological motif in these materials consists of elongated, rod-like aggregates [53,54,70]. The visual conception of the model is depicted in Fig. 10. V_{cylinder} and $V_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ are described by the equations Eq. (4) and Eq. (5), respectively. The aggregate has radius r_{AG} and length L_{AG} (L_{AG} is arbitrary). The amount of water (forming a shell with thickness of r_{W}) belonging to one aggregate is proportional to number of polymer backbone chains (N_{chain}) in the aggregate, molecular parameters of the polymer (EW , n_{TFE}) and values of λ (number of water molecules per $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$). The repeating unit is defined by its number of TFE segments n_{TFE} and their length l_{TFE} . Finally, $M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ denote molar mass and bulk density of water, and N_{A} is the Avogadro's number.

$$V_{\text{cylinder}} = L_{\text{AG}} \cdot \pi r_{\text{AG}}^2 + V_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \pi(r_{\text{AG}} + r_{\text{W}})^2 \cdot L_{\text{AG}} \quad (4)$$

$$V_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = \lambda_{\text{total}} \cdot \frac{L_{\text{AG}}}{n_{\text{TFE}} \cdot l_{\text{TFE}}} \cdot N_{\text{chain}} \cdot \frac{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{\rho_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \cdot N_{\text{A}}} \quad (5)$$

The model is based on the following assumptions.

- The membrane consists of cylindrical aggregates formed by polymer chains.

- Ionomer peak d -spacing from SAXS represents correlation distance between the cylindrical aggregates.
- Water forms a shell around the cylindrical aggregates. This shell is divided into two sub-shells corresponding to freezing and non-freezing water. The non-freezing water sub-shell can be at most three molecular layers thick.
- Spatial correlations between the cylindrical aggregates results in the signal of the ionomer peak observed in SAXS experiments; thus, the corresponding SAXS-derived d -spacing corresponds to the mean inter-aggregate distance.
- The diameter of the aggregate d_{AG} is equal to the ionomer peak d -spacing in the as-received state. This is based on an assumption that the as-received membranes contained no moisture during the SAXS measurement, likely resulting in a minor overestimation of d_{AG} values.
- The size of the aggregates (d_{AG} , N_{chain}) does not change upon activation but can vary as a result of the hydrothermally treatment.
- The interactions between $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups and water are fundamentally identical in all three membranes, and differences in water-state distributions are purely due to different membrane morphologies.

The model is included in the Supporting Excel file.

In the first step, the membranes were evaluated in their activated state. The diameter of the aggregate (d_{AG}) was taken as the d -spacing of the as-received membrane (this is equivalent to the distance between two adjacent aggregates). For each membrane, the number of polymer chains per aggregate (N_{chain}) was then adjusted such that the resulting cylinder's radius ($r_{\text{AG}} + r_{\text{W}}$) is equal to the d -spacing of the activated state (each chain brings certain amount of water corresponding to its number of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ groups and λ , increasing the overall cylinder volume). Using this approach, N_{chain} values in the range of 10–16 were obtained, depending on the membrane (see Table S3). The calculated water shell thickness (r_{W}) corresponded to approximately three molecular layers of water, indicating that, within this geometry, all water in the hydrophilic channels can exist in a non-freezing state. This result is consistent with the DSC data for activated Aquivion membranes (Fig. 8).

Using the obtained aggregate dimensions (N_{chain} and r_{AG}), it is possible to extract parameters suitable for comparison with literature data. The geometric model yields aggregate densities of 2.2, 3.2 and 3.3 g cm^{-3} for **AQE87**, **AQE98** and **N117**, respectively. PFSA polymer density values reported in the literature can be found to be around 2 g cm^{-3} [71–73]. Similarly, the inter-chain distances (within aggregate) derived from the model are 0.9, 0.7, and 0.8 nm for **AQE87**, **AQE98**, and **N117**, respectively. In a study by van der Heijden et al., chain spacings

Fig. 10. Illustration of the geometric model concept.

in an orthorhombic unit cell were reported to fall in the range of 0.6–1.0 nm [71]. Overall, the agreement with literature is relatively reasonable given the simplicity of the model.

In the next step, the model was applied to the hydrothermally treated membranes. Matching the ionomer peak d -spacing with the given water content in the treated membranes necessarily involves decreasing the number of aggregates. In principle, this can be achieved by two mechanisms: aggregate aggregation/coalescence or aggregate dissolution. The former option is in some studies considered to explain phenomena connected with PFSA membrane swelling (domain coalescence) [18, 58]. In the latter scenario, proposed here, a fraction of the aggregates dissolves into chaotically distributed smaller aggregates, while the remaining non-dissolved aggregates give rise to the SAXS ionomer-peak d -spacing. Thus, in both cases, swelling is accompanied by two concurrent processes – aggregate dilution and either aggregate aggregation/coalescence or dissolution – which together lead to the steep increase in the ionomer peak d -spacing with water content associated with the non-affine swelling discussed above.

To simulate the aggregate aggregation/coalescence, Eq. (6) was used to recalculate the dimensions of the new aggregates based on the values of N_{chain} and d_{AG} corresponding to the activated state. This scaling based on cylindrical geometry is analogous to the hexagonal close-packed structure observed in crystalline PTFE (Fig. S45) [74]. Analogically to the previous case, $N_{\text{chain, treated}}$ was adjusted so that the resulting cylinder dimensions matched the ionomer peak d -spacing in the treated state. However, this resulted in rather large polymeric aggregates, with $N_{\text{chain, treated}}$ equal to 26–40 and $d_{\text{AG, treated}}$ significantly exceeding the lengths of the side chains. Such a morphology would imply partial trapping of side chains within the aggregate cores, which should manifest as a decrease in ion-exchange capacity after hydrothermal treatment – an effect that was not observed experimentally (Fig. 2a). Moreover, the presence of large aggregates would result in too large water shell thickness, corresponding to 8–14 layers of water molecules, which is inconsistent with the DSC results. Therefore, the aggregate aggregation/coalescence does not explain our observations.

$$d_{\text{AG, treated}} = d_{\text{AG, activated}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{N_{\text{chain, treated}}}{N_{\text{chain, activated}}}} \quad (6)$$

In the next step, it was examined whether a partial aggregate dissolution could, in principle, explain the experimental observations. The aim of this calculation is to determine aggregate dimensions that agree with the experimentally observed amount of non-freezing water. Thus, the aggregate dimensions were scaled down by adjusting $N_{\text{chain, treated}}$ for each membrane in the treated state such that the resulting cylindrical geometry yielded a water-wall thickness r_{W} consistent with the experimentally determined amount of non-freezing water. This resulted in $N_{\text{chain, treated}}$ values of 2 and 4 for the Aquivions and 8 for N117. Although an aggregate consisting of only two chains is arguably very small, the calculations yielded physically plausible results. These results are also consistent with the d -spacing of the treated membranes, as all chaotically spaced smaller aggregates theoretically formed by dissolution can be accommodated between the non-dissolved aggregates (whose separation is defined by the ionomer-peak d -spacing) as demonstrated by the volume analysis in Section S5 of the Supporting Information.

On this basis, the high fractions of non-freezing water after the hydrothermal treatment can be rationalised by the presence of smaller aggregates composed of lower amount of polymer chains compared to the activated state. Assembly of such small aggregates results in very narrow hydrophilic channels, only few water molecules across. This morphology (combined with dilution effect) is expected to exhibit reduced connectivity between ion-exchange groups, lower local charge density, and increased tortuosity, which together can account for the observed degradation of charge-transport properties in Aquivion membranes. The lower susceptibility of N117 to the proposed aggregate

dissolution may be related to its longer side chains, which enable the formation of larger aggregates without side chains becoming trapped within the aggregate core.

3.7. Role of the α -transition temperature in overswelling

At this point, it is appropriate to revisit the role of the α -transition temperature (T_{α}), which, as noted in the introduction, strongly influences swelling. All three investigated membranes exhibit excessive water absorption, with the extent decreasing in the order AQE87 > N117 > AQE98. Interestingly, according to Moukheiber et al. [34], the T_{α} (of “dry” polymers) follow the order AQE98 > AQE87 > N117, with T_{α} of both Aquivion membranes exceeding 120 °C, while Nafion’s α -transition occurs just below 105 °C. This would suggest that exceeding the T_{α} is not necessary for the onset of overswelling.

To strengthen this conclusion, Table S4 summarises T_{α} values obtained by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) from multiple literature sources. For better illustration, Fig. 11 shows visual connection of the T_{α} found in literature with our experimental temperature. While there is certain ambiguity in the values, the T_{α} of the N117 membrane can be relatively safely assumed to lie below 120 °C (i.e., the experimental temperature used in this work), whereas the reported T_{α} values of AQE98 and AQE87 are above this temperature. It should be noted, however, that all reported T_{α} values correspond to “dry” or “as-received” membranes. As discussed in the introduction, when membranes are analysed by DMA under hydrated conditions (i.e., in a water vapour atmosphere), the viscoelastic peak associated with T_{α} disappears, indicating a fundamental change in the mechanical behaviour upon hydration. The underlying mechanism of this effect is not fully understood and lies beyond the scope of this study. However, dielectric spectroscopy studies on hydrated Nafion show that at relative humidity above 60% and temperature of 120 °C, Nafion undergoes a conformational change that can be attributed to its α -transition [30–32]. This suggests that, under hydrated conditions, the α -transition for Nafion is shifted to higher temperatures by approximately 20 °C (from ~100 °C to ~120 °C). A similar shift can be expected for Aquivions. Even without this expected shift, the temperature of the hydrothermal treatment applied in this study can be assumed to lie below T_{α} values for Aquivions. Another question is whether, and to what extent, the T_{α} values shift in response to the hydrothermal treatment. A shift (in whatever direction) can be expected, as internal structure of the membranes is severely changed during hydrothermal treatment. However, this would require dedicated study.

While our results suggest that exceeding T_{α} is not a necessary condition for the onset of overswelling, contrary to earlier assumptions [21, 22], it was clearly shown by multiple authors that when T_{α} is exceeded, the associated conformational changes allow further more pronounced water uptake [24,33]. The timescale of our experiments likely played a key role in the overswelling of the membranes – as shown in Fig. 1, steady state is not reached even after 800 h, indicating continued water absorption. Therefore, one can assume that excessive swelling can occur even below T_{α} if the polymer is exposed to liquid water for prolonged periods. It seems that excessive swelling is mainly driven by the polymer’s hydrophilicity and the reduced matrix stiffness at elevated temperatures (which acts against water uptake). Fascinating results consistent with this suggestion were presented by Fumagalli et al. [52]. They showed that Nafion 117 membrane did not reach equilibrium during swelling, even after six years of exposure to liquid water at 25 °C. They hypothesised that the osmotic pressure resulting from the absorbed water creates mechanical stress inside the membrane, analogous to a creep test, and that the lack of steady state during swelling is connected to ongoing plastic deformation.

Based on our conclusions, membrane stability in PEM water electrolysis at elevated temperatures and pressures should be improved by limiting the excessive water uptake. Increasing the EW can enhance the stability by reducing membrane hydrophilicity, but at the cost of ionic

T_α values reported in literature:

- dielectric spectroscopy — T_α hydrated Nafion — EW = ↓1100 g per SO_3^-
- dynamic mechanical analysis — T_α „dry“ Nafion — EW = ↓1020; ↓1100 g per SO_3^-
- dynamic mechanical analysis — T_α „dry“ Aquivion — EW = ↑815; ↑850-870; ↑895-910; ↑1100 g per SO_3^-

Fig. 11. Illustration of connection between the values of T_α reported in the literature (details and individual references are summarised in Table S4) and our experiment.

conductivity. Alternatively, covalent cross-linking of polymer chains may suppress swelling through mechanical constraint of the polymer network, while also negatively influencing ion transport by reducing chain mobility and ionic group accessibility. A combination of both approaches may also be considered.

4. Conclusion

Four commercial membranes were subjected to an 800-h hydrothermal treatment in liquid water at 120 °C and 600 kPa, with membrane resistance R_Ω continuously monitored. In addition to that, membranes were analysed by various methods including SAXS, WAXS and AFM. All treated membranes showed increase in R_Ω and loss of mechanical strength which can be attributed to observed morphological changes (crystallinity loss, volume expansion). Cast and reinforced **Fumapem F-940-RF** completely delaminated from its reinforcing mesh, indicating poor structural integrity, while extruded membranes (**Nafion 117**, **Aquivion E98-05S**, and **Aquivion E87-05S**) degraded less severely but still significantly.

Three key findings were identified in this study. First, the extent of performance degradation was not correlated with the α -transition temperature, contrary to expectations. Second, the degree of degradation associated with overswelling was primarily determined by the membrane's hydrophilicity (i.e. its equivalent weight). Third, the polymer side chain length influenced water accommodation within the membrane's internal nanostructure. Shorter side chains likely result in more tortuous and less connected ion-conducting pathways and smaller hydrophilic channels. The latter was indicated by DSC measurements, which showed a nearly negligible amount of bulk-like (freezing) water in membranes with short side chains. To explain the observations, a simple geometric model assuming a cylindrical morphology of PFSA chain aggregates surrounded by a layer of water was proposed.

The continuous increase in R_Ω indicated that water uptake in all membranes did not reach equilibrium even after 800 h of hydrothermal treatment. In PEM electrolyzers operated at elevated temperature and pressure, such persistent hydration (leading to overswelling) would likely cause ongoing membrane degradation and increase hydrogen permeability. These effects warrant further investigation.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Tereza Bautkinova: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Martin Prokop:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Tomas Bystron:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Vaclav Pokorny:** Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Zbynek Pientka:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Libuse Brozova:** Conceptualization. **Karel Bouzek:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the grammar and readability of the text. The authors subsequently reviewed and edited all content as necessary and take full responsibility for the final version of the manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2026.154316>.

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